

**LEADERSHIP STYLES AND MOTIVATION OF *BARANGAY* FUNCTIONARIES
IN DAVAO CITY**

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ABSTRACT

The study was conducted to determine the level of leadership styles and motivation of *barangay* functionaries in Davao city, Philippines. Quantitative non-experimental design using descriptive correlation method to 100 respondents among different *barangays*. Mean, Pearson-r and linear regression were the statistical tool used. Data analysis showed that the level of leadership styles for transformational leadership is very high and transactional leadership is high. Meanwhile, the level of motivation of *barangay* functionaries is high. There is a relationship between leadership styles and motivation of *barangay* functionaries. The regression model presented a significant influence leadership styles on the motivation of the *barangay* functionaries.

Keywords

Leadership Styles, Motivations, *Barangay* Functionaries, Descriptive Correlation, Regression Model, Davao City, Philippines

INTRODUCTION

The basic political unit in the Philippines is *Barangay*. It serves as the primary planning and implementing unit of government policies, plans, programs, projects, and activities in the community (Caldo, 2015). The *punong barangay* and the *Sangguniang Barangay* Members are considered as the highest government officials in the *Barangay* cluster. To help them render their service to the people through their leadership, they need the assistance of the *Barangay* Functionaries to execute their plans. The *Barangay* Functionaries are composed of *Barangay* Health Workers, *Barangay* Service Point Officers, *Barangay* Nutrition Scholars, Day Care Workers, and Civilian Volunteers Organizations.

As cited in the study of Caldo in 2015, based on a survey conducted by the DILG (May 2007), less than 50% of the *barangay* development councils are active and less than 70% of the *barangays* prepare a comprehensive *barangay* development plan. Major reason for this inactiveness is the lack of the capacity of the *Barangay* Development Council (BDC) to perform its mandated task. For this reason, most BDCs are in need of technical assistance in formulating the *barangay* development plan, and to ensure that the planning processes involve broader participation. Moreover, the capability of the BDC to execute its plan will reflect to the work motivation of the technical assistance that they seek from the *Barangay* Functionaries. As cited in the study of Kim (2000), Katzell & Thompson (1990) defined work motivation as “a broad construct pertaining to the conditions and processes that account for the arousal and direction, magnitude and maintenance of effort in a person's job. Knowing the fact that those employees play a vital role in the success of their organizations, their respective

employers must look after them as one of the main tasks that need appropriate managerial and leadership skills (Abdulhamid, 2017).

The study aims to determine the level of leadership styles and how it affects motivation of *barangay* functionaries in Davao City. Determining the leadership styles of the *barangay* officials in terms of transformational and transactional leadership and the aspects that affects the work motivation of the *barangay* functionaries in terms of job satisfaction, intrinsic job satisfaction, organizational commitment, conscientiousness, and timelessness and attendance are the major concern of this study.

Transformational Leadership. Hayati, Charkhabi and Naami (2014) stated that transformational leadership leads to make a positive effect by which, and by setting high standards, challenges the employees and establishes enthusiasm along with optimism for attaining success in works.

Transactional Leadership. According to Lipham and Rankin (2004), a leader should let the subordinates know what is expected of them, provides specific guidelines concerning what is to be done and how to do it, sets performance standards, arrange schedules and coordinates work.

Motivation. Munyeka (2014) states that motivation and inspiration boost people, by satisfying basic human needs for achievement, sense of belongingness, encouraging self-esteem and respecting control over one's life in contrast to pushing them in the direction as control mechanisms do.

FRAMEWORK

Various theories explain effectiveness of leadership. Among different types of leadership, transformational leadership and transactional leadership have been seen as strongly related with the employees' performance (Kirkman, Chen, Farh, Chen, & Lowe, 2009).

Inspirational motivation. This refers to the leader's ability to inspire confidence, motivation and a sense of purpose in his co-employees. These leaders are also able to help them experience the same passion and motivation to fulfill these goals (Wodehouse, 2018).

Idealized influence. It can be most expressed through a transformational leader's willingness to take risks and follow a core set of values, beliefs and ethical principles in the actions he takes (Riggio, 2014).

Intellectual stimulation. The leader supports his subordinates by involving them in the decision-making process and motivating them to be as creative and innovative as possible to identify resolutions (Besieux, 2019).

Individual consideration. The leader must be able to determine what motivates each individual. This is when leaders demonstrate genuine concern for the needs and feelings of followers. (Ogola, Sikalieh, & Linge, 2017).

Contingent reward. It is a motivation-based scheme that is used to reward those that meet their identified goals. This provides positive reinforcement for a job well done (Miller, 2015).

Management by exception. The top management is focused only on those areas in need of action. It keeps itself involved with the policy strategies & decisions (Pearson, 2018).

Laissez-faire leadership. In this type of leadership, leaders are hands-off and allow group members to make the decisions. Derived from the term is French for "let it be" or "leave alone," Simply letting the employees work in their own and allowing each one to exercise being independent (Harness, 2018).

General motivation. An individual's urge to behave or act in a way that will satisfy certain conditions, such as their own wishes, desires, or goals (Sincero, 2012).

Job satisfaction. The feeling of contentment or a sense of achievement, which an employee derives from his/her job. It is an emotional response that is the result of the interaction between the employees' values concerning their job and the profits they gain from their occupations (Kreitner, & Kinicki, 2012).

Intrinsic job satisfaction. This is defined as the attitude of the individual towards her/his field of work. It is when employees consider only the kind of work they do, the tasks that make up the job (Bektas, 2017).

Organizational commitment. This is the bond employees experience within their organization. Employees who are dedicated to their organization generally feel a connection with their organization, feel that they have the sense of belongingness, feel they understand the goals of the organization and that they willingly be part of attaining those (Singh & Gupta, 2015).

Conscientiousness. This is the tendency of an individual to have a sense of responsibility, being organized, hard-working, to be goal-oriented and to adhere to norms and rules (Harper, 2019).

Timeliness and attendance. Being present and on time gives an employer a great impression of an employee and it strengthens one's work credibility and work history. Timely and regular attendance is an expectation of performance for every employee (Smith, 2018).

OBJECTIVE OF THE STUDY

The study aims to determine the influence of leadership styles on the motivation of *barangay* functionaries in Davao city.

METHODOLOGY

Quantitative non-experimental design using descriptive correlation method was used in the study. Mean, Pearson-r and linear regression were the statistical tools utilized for the data analysis. The study was conducted among different *barangays* in Davao City, Philippines with 100 respondents.

RESULT AND DISCUSSION

This section presents the analysis and interpretation of data gathered.

Presented in Table 1 is the level of transformational leadership of *barangay* captains in Davao City which shows very high level with the overall mean rating of 4.34. This means that the *barangay* captains are perceptive in providing motivation and ascertaining the concerns of the *barangay* functionaries. This is verified by the statement of Hayati et al. (2014) that transformational leadership leads to make a positive effect by which, and by setting high standards, challenges the employees and establishes enthusiasm along with optimism for attaining success in works. Moreover, the survey manifested very high level on all the factors which means that the *barangay* captains have been effective in their transformational leadership.

Table 1. Level of Transformational Leadership of Barangay Captain

Transformational Leadership	SD	Mean	Description
1. Inspirational Motivation	0.70	4.43	Very High
2. Idealized Influence	0.64	4.32	Very High
3. Intellectual Stimulation	0.74	4.35	Very High
4. Individual Consideration	0.89	4.24	Very High
Overall	0.61	4.34	Very High

Presented in Table 1.1 is the *barangay* captains in Davao City practiced transactional leadership to a high level with an overall mean rating of 4.18. This means that *barangay* captains are expecting quality performance from the *barangay* functionaries by providing them with the necessary knowledge on the standards needed to carry out the work. This affirms to Lipham and Rankin (2004), a leader should let the subordinates know what is expected of them, provides specific guidelines concerning what is to be done and how to do it, sets performance standards, arrange schedules and coordinates work. Additionally, the result implies a high level of job satisfaction among the *barangay* functionaries and manifested that they are rewarded and recognized for their good performance.

Table 1.1. Level of Transactional Leadership of Barangay Captain

Transactional Leadership	SD	Mean	Description
1. Contingent reward	0.81	4.10	High
2. Management by exception	0.71	4.29	Very High
3. Laissez-faire leadership	0.83	4.13	High
4. Job satisfaction	0.76	4.20	High
Overall	0.78	4.18	High

Presented in Table 2 is the high level of motivation among *barangay* functionaries in Davao City with an average mean rating of 4.16. This indicates that they are highly motivated in their work causing them to become committed to their task being performed. As what Muniyeka (2014) stated, motivation and inspiration boost people, by satisfying basic human needs for achievement, sense of belongingness, encouraging self-esteem and respecting control over one's life in contrast to pushing them in the direction as control mechanisms do. Moreover, it emphasizes a very high level of job satisfaction among the *barangay* functionaries with an average of 4.22 which means that they are satisfied with their tasks, colleagues and Supervisors.

Table 2. Level of Motivation of Barangay Functionaries

Motivation	SD	Mean	Description
1. General motivation	0.78	4.16	High
2. Job satisfaction	0.79	4.22	Very High
3. Intrinsic job satisfaction	0.91	4.18	High
4. Organizational commitment	0.75	4.17	High
5. Conscientiousness	0.79	4.20	High
6. Timeliness and attendance	0.85	4.02	High
Overall	0.81	4.16	High

Presented in Table 3 is the relationship between leadership styles and motivations of *barangay* functionaries in Davao City. It indicates that the strength of association between the variable is positively correlated with the R-value of .578 and the p-value of .000 which is lesser than .05 level of significance. This implies that the increase in leadership styles, the level of motivation among the *barangay* functionaries.

Transactional and transformational leaderships as domains of leadership styles significantly correlated to the motivation of the *barangay* functionaries as revealed in the R-values of .659 and .654 respectively. The R-values are .000 which is lesser than .05 level of significance. This implies that the level of motivation of *barangay* functionaries is dependent on these dimensions.

Table 3. Relationship between Leadership Styles and Motivations of Barangay Functionaries

Leadership Style	Motivations		Decision on Ho
Transformational	Person Correlation	.659**	Significant
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	
Inspirational Motivation	Person Correlation	.635**	Significant
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	
Idealized Influence	Person Correlation	.573**	Significant
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	
Intellectual Simulation	Person Correlation	.477**	Significant
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	
Individual Consideration	Person Correlation	.505**	Significant
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	
Transactional	Person Correlation	.654**	Significant
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	
Contingent Reward	Person Correlation	.565**	Significant
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	
Management by exception	Person Correlation	.626**	Significant
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	
Laissez-faire leadership	Person Correlation	.616**	Significant
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	
Job satisfaction	Person Correlation	.627**	Significant
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000**	
Overall	Person Correlation	0.578	Significant
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000**	

Presented in Table 4 is the regression analysis of leadership styles and motivation which shows that transactional leadership can singly influence the motivation of the *barangay* functionaries as shown in p-value of .000 which is lower than 0.05 level of significance. However, transformational leadership cannot alone

influence the motivation of *barangay* functionaries as revealed in the p-value of .099 which is greater than .05 level of significance

Meanwhile, as shown in the F-value of 57.483 and p-value of 0.000 which is less than 0.000 level of significance. This implies that leadership styles are gather together it will be enough to have a significant influence on the motivation of *barangay* functionaries. The r-square value of 0.736 or equivalent to 73.6% means that the variance of 26.4% is attributed to other factors not covered in this study. The regression Equation: $Y = 0.038 + .267X_1 + .727X_2$ can be modelled to predict the increase of motivation.

Table 4. Leadership Styles and Motivation of Barangay Functionaries

Leadership Styles	Motivation			Decision on Ho
	Beta	t-value	p-value	
Transformational Leadership	0.267	1.664	0.099	Accept Ho
Transactional Leadership	.727	4.796	0.000	Reject Ho
R-square: 0.736		F-value: 57.483	p-value: 0.000	
Regression Equation: $Y = 0.038 + .267X_1 + .727X_2$				

CONCLUSION

The study concluded that the level of leadership styles is very high and the level of motivation of *barangay* functionaries is high. Both transitional and transformational leaderships are positively correlated to the motivation of *barangay* functionaries. Moreover, the regression model depicts significant influence of leadership styles on the motivation of *barangay* functionaries. However, transactional leadership can singly influence the motivation of the *barangay* functionaries. Conversely, this study may contribute to the administrative division in Davao City that having transactional leadership style may signify positive role in motivating the *barangay* functionaries.

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